

Guideline for questions used for expert interviews conducted in 2023 by Tanja Wissik within the project “Study on Terminology Workflows in the 21st Century”. These questions are based on the questions of a previous study on terminology workflows (Chiocchetti & Ralli, 2012, Attachment A¹).

¹ Chiocchetti, E. & Ralli, N. (2012). Deliverable D3.2 Report Workflow Adaptation for LISE.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/projects/cnect/7/270917/080/deliverables/001-LISEdeliverable32.pdf>

Guideline for Questions (v1.0)

GENERAL ASPECTS

What is your background and how long do you already work with terminology?

For how many years has your institution been dealing with terminology?

Who does terminology work (translators, professional terminologists, others, etc.)?

Are there native speakers for all languages managed?

What kind of education/training do these people have (degree in translation/terminology, specific subject field...)?

How many staff members (full time/part time) are there in the terminology service/do terminology work?

Is continuous training available for staff members?

When is terminology work necessary?

Why does the institution manage terminology?

Who are the target users (e.g., internal personnel/public; language experts/subject field experts, NLP/AI experts etc.)?

Do you collaborate with Research Infrastructures such as CLARIN or DARIAH or other projects/initiatives?

METHODOLOGY

Is the approach descriptive or prescriptive?

Is terminology work done systematically or ad hoc or both?

Who solves monolingual/multilingual terminology issues (translators, terminologists, subject field experts, etc.)?

Who creates/discusses/validates neologisms?

Which steps are done automatically/manually (e.g., terminology extraction)?

Which material/documents is the work based on?

Do you use corpora and corpus tools ? Do you build your own corpora or do you reuse corpora? Where do you search for corpora? If you use your own corpora, do you publish them as well (e.g. licence?).

Do you use ISO and/or national standards? Do you have access to them?

TERMINOLOGY MANAGEMENT

Is the work coordinated centrally in one service or are several departments collecting their own terminology collections?

Who is in charge of terminology management?

Who revises the terminology (senior terminologists, subject field experts, etc.)? Is it done inside the terminology management system or outside (e.g., spreadsheet)?

How are entries corrected/updated (manually/automatically, selectively/batch changes)?

Which roles are clearly defined? Are there any?

How are these roles defined (e.g., are terminologists there to feed a database? to create, organise and centralise the terminology?)?

What are the quality assurance / revision steps?

Are there specific (written) internal/public guidelines for some or all of the aspects related to terminology work?

How is the collaboration with external experts (e.g., for revision) organised?

What is the role of IT experts and how is the collaboration organised?

Do you collaborate with experts in language technology/Natural Language Processing //Artificial Intelligence?

Is there any collaboration with the user (e.g., suggestion function for new terms in the term base)?

Do you have experience with crowdsourcing for terminology work?

Is there one (or more) standard workflow for terminology production?

What does it look like? Which tools are used and how are they employed?

What kinds of problems do you face with this/these type(s) of workflow, if any?

How is your terminology published/disseminated and who has access (term base, dictionaries, downloadable as data export etc.)?

How are new languages added (manually/automatically, selectively/batch changes)?

Harmonising or merging databases: how do you proceed (manually, semi-automatically)? What are the workflow steps and what problems do/did you face, if any?

When making software changes, migrating to a new term base /platform etc., how is this organised?

Is the data accessible via an API? Or if not, did the question of providing an API came up lately?

Terminology Management Systems and other technology

Is there an internal/online term base? Which technology it is based on (e.g., commercial, open source)?

If you need a new feature in your term base or other system, what do you do?

Is the system you are working with internally the same that is accessible for the public?

What does the data model look like?

What does the entry structure look like?

Which tools do you use beside a Terminology Management System?

Do you use a workflow system?

Which formats/standards are used?

Is the data from the term base also downloadable for externals (licence, format etc.)

Is the data openly available?

Does Machine Translation play a role in your work?

Does Semantic Web Technologies play a role in your work?

Is your terminology also published as linked data?

Is the terminology data stored/archived in a repository?

Standardisation

Is the collected terminology standardised by some responsible body?

Are there specific guidelines for terminology standardisation?

How is the standardisation process/workflow organised (commission, experts, meetings between terminologists and experts, online communication/forum, etc.)?

Tanja Wissik

Study on Terminology Workflows in the 21st Century

Relation with Lexicography Work

If in your institution also lexicography work is done, is there any collaboration?

Do you use the same tools and / or resources (e.g., corpora)?